

Root and shoot growth of *Oryza sativa* L. as affected by redox potential

N. Sekhon, H. S. Sur, and N. T. Singh, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

We compared root and shoot growth responses to levels of soil reduction.

Iron pots 1 m high and 50 cm in diameter were uniformly packed with a loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) and different levels of redox potential created using the treatments control (soil kept near 60% field capacity), submergence (4-6 cm standing water), submergence + 0.5% starch, and submergence + 1% starch. One day after treatment, 21 seedlings of cultivar PR106 were transplanted into each pot. Recommended doses of fertilizers were used. All measures, except shoot and

Effect of soil redox potential on rice roots and shoots.^a Ludhiana, India.

Treatment	Soil Eh (mV)	Root porosity (%)	Tillers (no./plant)	Plant ht (cm)	Leaf area (dm ² /plant)	Total chlorophyll (mg/g fresh wt)	Root density (µg/cm ³)	Straw yield (g/pot)	Grain yield (g/pot)
Control	+343	7.8 b	5.5 b	74.4 b	6.3 b	4.1 b	498 b	165 c	98 b
Submergence (S)	+70	12.9 a	6.0 a	84.3 a	1.5 a	4.2 b	735 a	208 b	221 a
S + 0.5% starch	-91	13.2 a	6.8 a	84.8 a	8.3 a	5.1 a	847 a	287 a	264 a
S + 1% starch	-396	15.2 a	5.8 a	82.3 a	7.7 a	5.3 a	792 a	259 a	242 a

^aIn a column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

grain weight, were recorded at panicle emergence.

The redox potentials created ranged from +343 mV to -396 (see table). Decrease in Eh from +343 to +70 mV significantly improved growth measures except for total chlorophyll content. Lowering Eh to -97 mV further improved all measures including the chlorophyll content. Further decrease in redox potential did not improve growth but significantly reduced tillers, leaf

area, and root density. The amount of roots increased in the surface 5-cm soil layer with decrease in redox potential from +343 to -3% mV.

Growth improvement with decrease in Eh to -97 mV could be explained by better tissue hydration, higher availability and uptake of nutrients, and improved soil physical conditions. Further reduction may lead to accumulation of toxic products. □

Crop management

Effect of irrigation, and seedling age and number on rice yield

A. S. Sidhu, G. C. Aggarwal, and N. T. Singh, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

Using variety PR106 on a calcareous sandy loam soil (Typic Ustochrept), we laid out treatments with three replications in a split-plot design.

Irrigation was in the main plot and combinations of seedling age and number per hill in the subplots. Irrigation levels were daily irrigation (I₁), irrigation on alternate days (I₂), and irrigation after 2 d (I₃). Seedling ages were 32, 45, and 57 d and seedling rates were 2 and 3 per hill. The nursery was transplanted 5 Jul. NPK was applied at 120-18-25 kg/ha. Irrigation treatments began, after 3 wk of continuous submergence after transplanting, with 259 cm applied in I₁, 210 cm in I₂, and 181 cm in I₃. The soil had 8.0 pH, low

Table 1. Effect of irrigation, and seedling age and number per hill on rice yield. Ludhiana, India, 1988.

	Rice yield (t/ha)		
	2 seedlings/hill	3 seedlings/hill	Mean
Irrigation			
I ₁	10.2	10.1	10.1
I ₂	9.6	9.9	9.8
I ₃	9.1	9.5	9.3
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.1	ns	0.1
Seedling age (d)			
32	10.1	10.1	10.0
45	9.4	9.6	9.5
57	9.4	9.7	10.0
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.5	ns	0.4

organic C (0.3%), and medium available P (14.5 kg P/ha) and available K (136 kg K/ha).

Rice yields were significantly better with daily irrigation (Table 1), but only with 2 seedlings/hill. Similarly, yields were better with younger (32 d) seedlings, but only with 2/hill. Results indicate that transplanting 3 seedlings/hill ameliorated the adverse effect of decreased irrigation as well as of advanced seedling age. Irrigation

Table 2. Interactive effect of irrigation and seedling age on rice yield. Ludhiana, India, 1988.

Seedling age (d)	Rice yield (t/ha)			LSD (P = 0.05)
	I ₁	I ₂	I ₃	
32	10.6	10.1	9.4	0.9
45	9.8	9.6	9.2	ns
57	10.0	9.5	9.3	ns
Mean	10.1	9.8	9.3	0.6

frequency was significant only when younger seedlings (32 d old) were transplanted (Table 2). □

Rice response to N rates and delayed planting

A. K. Pande and R. C. Gautam, Agronomy Department, G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Nainital 263145, U.P., India

Usually kharif rice planted late, with the onset of monsoon, yields less. We studied whether variety duration and N rate can compensate for later planting.

In 1985 wet season at the Crop Research Center (29°N, 79.3°E, and

Table 1. Atmospheric temperature, rainfall, and solar radiation during planting time. Nainital, U. P., India, 1985 wet season.

Date	Temperature (°C)		Rainfall (mm)	Sunshine (h/d)
	Maximum	Minimum		
18-24 Jun	40.0	27.7	26.4	6.7
25- 1 Jun	35.1	24.7	48.7	8.8
2- 8 Jul	33.2	25.4	54.4	5.3
9-15 Jul	31.1	24.7	113.0	5.5
16-22 Jul	31.1	24.6	129.9	6.1

243.8 m altitude), we used Beni silty clay loam, fine-silty, mixed, hyperthermic, Aquic Hapludoll with pH 7.5, 1.3% organic C, 0.11% total N, 15.82 kg available (Olsen) P/ha, and 139.68 kg available K/ha. The region enjoys subhumid subtropical climate with high temperature in May-Jun and heavy rainfall during Jul-Aug (Table 1). Twelve treatment combinations—three

planting dates, two varieties and two N rates—were compared in a randomized block design (Table 2). Varieties Govind and Pant Dhan 4 differed in duration (105 and 130 d).

Significantly higher grain yield was obtained with early planting, high N, and with a short-duration variety under delayed planting. □

Table 2. Grain yield as influenced by planting date, variety, and N rate. Nainital, India, 1985 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Planting date</i> ^a	
25 Jun	5.4
5 Jul	4.8
15 Jul	3.9
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3
<i>Variety</i>	
Pant Dhan 4	4.2
Govind	5.2
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.2
<i>N rate (kg/ha)</i>	
60	4.4
120	5.0
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.2
CV (%)	7.8

^aSeed sowing date in nursery.

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Effect of N source and application time on rice

N. A. Salam, E. Tajuddin, K. Varghese, S. M. S. Hameed, and Y. Thomas, Kerala Agricultural University, Karamana 695002, Trivandrum, India

We studied effects of N sources and application times on Jaya rice grain and straw yields during 1987 kharif (Jun-Sep) at the Cropping Systems Research

Center, Trivandrum (11°N, 77°E, 30 m above mean sea level). We used 3 sources of N at 90 kg N/ha and 4 application times (see table). The basal application was broadcast and incorporated at transplanting time. For topdressing, all sources were broadcast, keeping soil moist and gradually increasing the water level to 2-3 cm. The soil (sandy clay loam, riverine alluvium deposited over laterite soil) contained 0.47% organic C, 120-7.7-58 ppm of

available NPK, and 390 ppm total soil N, with a pH of 5.2 and EC of 0.25 dS/m.

Results show N impact differed with source and with application time. PU gave higher grain (14% moisture) and straw yields when applied in 3 splits (1/3 basal + 1/3 at tillering + 1/3 at panicle initiation). MPCU should be applied entirely as basal or in 2 splits (1/2 basal + 1/2 at tillering). LGU gave best yields when applied in 2 splits (1/2 basal + 1/2 at tillering) or in 3 splits (1/2 basal + 1/4 at tillering + 1/4 at panicle initiation). □

Grain and straw yields as influenced by time of application and source^a of urea. Trivandrum, India, Jun-Sep, 1987.

Time ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)				Straw yield (t/ha)			
	PU	MPCU	LGU	Mean	PU	MPCU	LGU	Mean
Full basal	3.0	3.4	3.0	3.1	4.2	4.1	5.0	4.5
1/2 B + 1/2 T	3.0	3.5	3.7	3.4	6.3	5.1	5.6	5.6
1/2 B + 1/4 T + 1/4 PI	2.6	2.6	3.7	3.0	4.4	5.6	5.7	5.2
1/3 B + 1/3 T + 1/3 PI	3.3	2.9	2.7	3.0	4.9	4.6	4.0	4.5
	3.0	3.1	3.3		4.9	4.8	5.1	
	LSD (0.05)				LSD (0.05)			
Time (T)	0.3			Time (T)	0.5			
Source (S)	ns			Source (S)	ns			
T × S	0.5			T × S	0.9			

^aPU = prilled urea, MPCU = Mussoorie phosphate-coated urea, LGU = large granule urea. ^bB = basal, T = tillering, PI = panicle initiation.

Estimation of pH, ammonium N, and nitrate N of floodwater with integrated N management of lowland rice

B. S. Mahapatra, K. C. Sharma, and G. L. Sharma Agronomy Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Nainital 263145, U.P., India

Ammonium N and nitrate N in floodwater reflect the N loss that occurs easily in a submerged soil-water system common to lowland rice. The extent of